

1. Participant ID Number _____
2. Date of birth (dd/mm/yyyy)_____
3. Sex: M/F/N _____
4. Date of interview (dd/mm/yyyy)_____
5. Interviewer's name_____

Why do we ask these questions?

We are interested in improving health, especially oral health. In this study, we are exploring the microorganisms (such as bacteria, viruses, and other small organisms) that live in your mouth and how this may be related to how you live and your health. In particular, we are investigating how your lifestyle can impact the bacteria in your mouth that can cause periodontal disease.

The information that you provide today will be incredibly useful when we try to understand how different lifestyles impact different types of bacteria, and how these signals are linked to oral health. We will also be exploring which bacteria can cause oral disease, such as periodontal disease. Together, this information will help us understand how and why periodontal disease occurs in Romanians.

Everything you say is confidential. We do not collect your name with the answers, so we collect only what has been said, but not who said it.

If you have any questions, please ask. We want you to feel relaxed.

INSTRUCTIONS

The QUESTIONNAIRE

This questionnaire asks about your background, diet, general health, and oral health. We would like you to complete the questionnaire even if you have good dental health.

HOW TO ANSWER THE QUESTIONS

Each question is on the left side of the page and is inside a grey box. Some questions have boxes. You can answer these questions by either shading or marking the box to indicate your answer. Other questions will require you to write in your response. Please right in the designated area to answer these questions.

EXAMPLES

A1. What is your nationality?	Romanian <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Multiple <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/>
A4. What city are you currently living and how long have you lived there?			
Bucharest 5 years			

A. THESE QUESTIONS ARE ABOUT YOUR BACKGROUND				
We are ask these questions about your background because they may provide useful information in understanding your oral health and bacteria.				
A1. What is your nationality?	Romanian <input type="checkbox"/>	Multiple <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/>	
A2. What your first language?	Romanian <input type="checkbox"/>	Multiple <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/>	
A3. Usual place of residence	Urban <input type="checkbox"/>	Rural <input type="checkbox"/>	Suburban <input type="checkbox"/>	Not sure <input type="checkbox"/>
A4. What city are you currently living and how long have you lived there?				
A5. If you had lived in other cities, when did you live there and for how long?				

A6. What level of education have you completed?	No formal schooling..... <input type="checkbox"/>			
	High schooling completed..... <input type="checkbox"/>			
	College/University completed..... <input type="checkbox"/>			
	Postgraduate degree..... <input type="checkbox"/>			
A7. What is your main source of drinking water?	Urban tap water <input type="checkbox"/>	Rural tap water <input type="checkbox"/>	Bottled water <input type="checkbox"/>	Other <input type="checkbox"/> Please specify: <hr/>
	A8. During the last year, have you avoided or delayed visiting a dentist because of cost?		Yes <input type="checkbox"/> ₁	No <input type="checkbox"/> ₂
A9. How much difficulty would you have paying a €100 dental bill?	None <input type="checkbox"/>	Hardly any <input type="checkbox"/>	A little <input type="checkbox"/>	Very difficult <input type="checkbox"/>

B. THESE QUESTIONS ARE ABOUT YOUR DIET						
How often do you consume the following items?						
B1. Fresh fruit	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Did in the past, but have stopped for more than one year <input type="checkbox"/>	
	B2. Fresh vegetables	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Did in the past, but have stopped for more than one year <input type="checkbox"/>

B3. Store bought sweets/candy	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Did in the past, but have stopped for more than one year <input type="checkbox"/>
B4. Home baked sweets	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Did in the past, but have stopped for more than one year <input type="checkbox"/>
B5. Soft drinks such as Coca Cola	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Did in the past, but have stopped for more than one year <input type="checkbox"/>
B6. Hot Green Tea	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Did in the past, but have stopped for more than one year <input type="checkbox"/>
B7. Hot Black Tea	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Did in the past, but have stopped for more than one year <input type="checkbox"/>
B8. Coffee	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Did in the past, but have stopped for more than one year <input type="checkbox"/>
B9. Meat	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Did in the past, but have stopped for more than one year <input type="checkbox"/>
B10. Milk	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Did in the past, but have stopped for more than one year <input type="checkbox"/>
B11. Fermented dairy (e.g. yogurt or cheese)	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Did in the past, but have stopped for more than one year <input type="checkbox"/>

B11. Fermented foods	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Did in the past, but have stopped for more than one year <input type="checkbox"/>
How often do you use any of the following types of products (Read each item)					
B12. Cigarettes or Cigars	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Did in the past, but have stopped for more than one year <input type="checkbox"/>
B13. Chewing tobacco	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Did in the past, but have stopped for more than one year <input type="checkbox"/>
B14. Electronic cigarettes	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Did in the past, but have stopped for more than one year <input type="checkbox"/>
B15.a. Alcohol	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Did in the past, but have stopped for more than one year <input type="checkbox"/>
B15.b. What types of alcohol do you drink? List all that apply	_____				

C. GENERAL HEALTH			
We ask these questions about your general health because your general health influences your microbes.			
C1. Are you currently taking medication for anything?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> ₁	No <input type="checkbox"/> ₂	Rather not say <input type="checkbox"/> ₃

C2. If so, what medications are you taking.		_____	
C3. Do you have a current OR have you recovered from a recent infection within the last 3 months? (Not including COVID-19)	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> ₁	No <input type="checkbox"/> ₂	Rather not say <input type="checkbox"/> ₃
C4.a. Have you ever tested positive for COVID-19?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> ₁	No <input type="checkbox"/> ₂	Rather not say <input type="checkbox"/> ₃
C4.b. If so, how long ago were you tested?	_____		
C5. Do you currently use any medications to treat inflammation?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> ₁	No <input type="checkbox"/> ₂	Rather not say <input type="checkbox"/> ₃
C6. Have you taken any antibiotics in the past six months?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> ₁	No <input type="checkbox"/> ₂	Rather not say <input type="checkbox"/> ₃
C7.a. Have you been diagnosed with any systemic diseases?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> ₁	No <input type="checkbox"/> ₂	Rather not say <input type="checkbox"/> ₃
C7.b. If so, what is it?	Please specify _____		

D. ORAL HEALTH PERCEPTIONS

We are asking these questions because your oral health and the microbes within your mouth are connected.

During the last 12 months have you had (tick all that apply)

D1. Would you rate your oral health as:		Excellent	<input type="checkbox"/>		
		Very good	<input type="checkbox"/>		
		Good	<input type="checkbox"/>		
		Average	<input type="checkbox"/>		
		Poor	<input type="checkbox"/>		
		Very poor	<input type="checkbox"/>		
D2. How would you describe the state of your teeth and gums?			Teeth	Gums	
		Excellent	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		Very good	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		Good	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		Average	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
		Poor	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
D3. A bad taste in your mouth		Yes	No	Rather not say	
		<input type="checkbox"/> ₁	<input type="checkbox"/> ₂	<input type="checkbox"/> ₃	
D4. How often do your gums bleed?	Never	Hardly ever	Occasionally	Fairly often	Very often
	<input type="checkbox"/> ₁	<input type="checkbox"/> ₂	<input type="checkbox"/> ₃	<input type="checkbox"/> ₄	<input type="checkbox"/> ₅
D5. How often do you see a dentist?	Very often	Fairly often	Occasionally	Hardly ever	Never
	<input type="checkbox"/>				
D6. How many natural teeth do you have?	0 natural teeth	1-9 teeth	10-19 teeth	20 or more teeth	
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

					<input type="checkbox"/>
D7. Do you have any removable dentures?	A partial denture <input type="checkbox"/>	A full upper denture <input type="checkbox"/>	A full lower denture <input type="checkbox"/>	A full upper and lower denture <input type="checkbox"/>	
D8. How often do you clean your teeth?	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Did in the past, but have stopped for more than one year <input type="checkbox"/>
D9.a. Do you use any of the following to clean your teeth? (Read each item)				Yes	No
		Toothbrush.....		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		Wooden toothpicks.....		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		Plastic toothpicks.....		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		Thread (dental floss)		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Mouthwash.....		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
D9.b. Other(s) (Please specify)	_____				
D9.c. If you use a toothbrush, do you use toothpaste?	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>			No <input type="checkbox"/>	
D9.d. If you use mouth rinse, how often do you use it?	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>	Daily <input type="checkbox"/>	Did in the past, but have stopped for more than one year <input type="checkbox"/>
D9.e. What is the name of the mouth rinse you use?	_____				

D10. Have you had trouble <u>pronouncing any words</u> because of problems with your teeth, mouth, or dentures?	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Hardly ever <input type="checkbox"/>	Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/>	Fairly often <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Often <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't Know <input type="checkbox"/>
D11. Have you felt that your <u>sense of taste</u> has worsened because of problems with your teeth, mouth, or dentures?	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Hardly ever <input type="checkbox"/>	Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/>	Fairly often <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Often <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't Know <input type="checkbox"/>
D12. Have you had <u>painful aching</u> in your mouth?	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Hardly ever <input type="checkbox"/>	Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/>	Fairly often <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Often <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't Know <input type="checkbox"/>
D13. Have you found it <u>uncomfortable to eat any foods</u> because of problems with your teeth, mouth, or dentures?	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Hardly ever <input type="checkbox"/>	Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/>	Fairly often <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Often <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't Know <input type="checkbox"/>
D14. Have you been <u>self-conscious</u> because of your teeth, mouth, or dentures?	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Hardly ever <input type="checkbox"/>	Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/>	Fairly often <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Often <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't Know <input type="checkbox"/>
D15. Have you <u>felt tense</u> because of problems with your teeth, mouth, or dentures?	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Hardly ever <input type="checkbox"/>	Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/>	Fairly often <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Often <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't Know <input type="checkbox"/>

D16. Has your <u>diet been unsatisfactory</u> because of problems with your teeth, mouth, or dentures?	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Hardly ever <input type="checkbox"/>	Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/>	Fairly often <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Often <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't Know <input type="checkbox"/>
D17. Have you had to <u>interrupt meals</u> because of problems with your teeth, mouth, or dentures?	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Hardly ever <input type="checkbox"/>	Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/>	Fairly often <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Often <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't Know <input type="checkbox"/>
D18. Have you found it <u>difficult to relax</u> because of problems with your teeth, mouth, or dentures?	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Hardly ever <input type="checkbox"/>	Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/>	Fairly often <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Often <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't Know <input type="checkbox"/>
D19. Have you been a bit <u>embarrassed</u> because of problems with your teeth, mouth, or dentures?	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Hardly ever <input type="checkbox"/>	Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/>	Fairly often <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Often <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't Know <input type="checkbox"/>
D20. Have you been a bit <u>irritable with other people</u> because of problems with your teeth, mouth, or dentures?	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Hardly ever <input type="checkbox"/>	Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/>	Fairly often <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Often <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't Know <input type="checkbox"/>
D21. Have you had <u>difficulty doing your usual jobs</u> because of problems with your teeth, mouth, or dentures?	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Hardly ever <input type="checkbox"/>	Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/>	Fairly often <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Often <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't Know <input type="checkbox"/>

D22. Have you felt that life in general was <u>less satisfying</u> because of problems with your teeth, mouth, or dentures?	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Hardly ever <input type="checkbox"/>	Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/>	Fairly often <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Often <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't Know <input type="checkbox"/>
D23. Have you been <u>totally unable to function</u> because of problems with your teeth, mouth, or dentures?	Never <input type="checkbox"/>	Hardly ever <input type="checkbox"/>	Occasionally <input type="checkbox"/>	Fairly often <input type="checkbox"/>	Very Often <input type="checkbox"/>	Don't Know <input type="checkbox"/>